

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMBRIS-DICK****FIRST NAME: SYLNA****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the MSWord on Windows 10

List your five (5) key concepts with page number in text:

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One? (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-42)

NAVIGATING ACADEMIC WRITING: KEY PROPELLERS

1) INTRODUCTION

My first course with Euclid University is 'International Academic Writing, *ACA-401D*'. It consists of seven (7) Periods for which I must study various materials and carry out several assignments. This Response Paper (RP) One (1) is prepared in compliance with the first assigned task. I am required to review the assigned Coursepack, watch the videos and prepare the RP based on standard Euclid guidelines and the required template. The purpose of the *ACA-401D* has both short- and long-term scope. For immediate purposes, it provides essential knowledge by plunging students into the standards required for academic writing at Euclid University. A more overarching aim is to skilfully lead students into the substantive and formal outputs that must be submitted for future course work, as well as producing professional growth outside of academia (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 3).

Having been allowed to choose a topic based on the contents of the *ACA-401D* coursepack, which is in its fifth edition, my choice for this RP is 'Navigating Academic Writing: Key Propellers'. I crafted this theme in response to my initial attempts at gathering, filing and assimilating the swathe of information on this new stage of my

academic journey while trying to ensure that other areas of my life remain afloat. Although some areas are familiar, I will allow the Turabian academic writing style to light the un-journeyed Arabian nights of this new adventure with Euclid University. Whether airborne or caught in swirling dunes, I anticipate pushing through each phase of my studies to reach the oasis of being credentialed in the sciences.

In this RP One (RP1), I explore five significant concepts in essay writing. They are culled from the information provided to me in the first Coursepack on my enrolment with Euclid University. After summarising key aspects of these concepts, I present my understanding of their importance and relevance to my academic and professional journey. In relation to the required video for viewing, information was given on how to use the templates provided in preparing response papers (Cleenewerck 2016).

2) ESSAY WRITING

Chapter One of the coursepack outlines some core elements of essay writing, identifies the steps necessary to create a good essay, and presents recommendations when writing a paper. The intention here is to introduce core elements of essay writing to students. This should not be slighted by persons with extensive experience in academic writing, as Euclid University must cater to a wide variety of students from diverse backgrounds.

The Chapter indicates that writing an essay is a non-linear process that involves multiple steps. Core aspects of this process include analysing the issue to be explored, setting out the author's perspective, carrying out research based on high-quality academic sources, creating an essay plan which itemises the various segments to be written, drafting and editing, referencing and submission (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 8).

I agree with the authors on the importance of the preparatory stage of writing an essay, as failure to comprehend and define the most critical concepts will lead to an unfocussed approach and irrelevant key issues. This, in turn, will cascade into conducting wrong diagnostics, presenting inappropriate results and loss of quality academic time. I also support the emphasis on adequately reading and researching the topic, as the papers for my climate change and sustainability degree must be scientifically sound. Supporting data from multiple credible sources may include statistics and case studies, which I must diligently curate and present in developing my thesis and presenting my findings. The critical thinking needed to produce these results should blend with my creativity. Thus, the scientific evidence and my mind mapping and research skills will converge to present an academically robust and standard-compliant essay.

I must admit that I initially smirked a bit on reading the final essay submission step! However, on reflection, my grin quickly disappeared with my recognition that some students face challenges in completing their courses of study. Given my other competing responsibilities, this harsh possibility spurs me to ensure that all my work is conducted on time.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Chapter Two addresses the issue of punctuation. It sets out a general rule which aims to balance the amount of punctuation used in a sentence to minimise skewing the meaning of what is written. A rule that is of personal interest to me is not to use bullet points at the end of a list of items; however, a full stop is required at the end of the last point if the text that comes before all the bullet points forms a complete sentence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 18).

This is an example of a writing habit that I must abandon as I am accustomed to placing a semi-colon after each bullet point, whether a complete sentence precedes it or not. This tendency would have arisen from not remembering the rules for preparing PowerPoint presentations. Additionally, my training as a legislative drafter requires me to place a semi-colon after each legislative paragraph. Each legislative paragraph would, of course, have been preceded by a complete sentence.

The importance of using correct punctuation is therefore re-emphasised to me. There is undoubtedly some convergence between punctuation rules applicable to academic writing and legislative drafting. On the other hand, both writing genres attest to the need for a sentence to be in plain, unambiguous language, with accurate punctuation that will allow the reader to interpret the message being communicated.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Chapter Three emphasises the importance of selecting between American Standard English (ASE) and British Standard English (BSE), both of which emerged from World English. Academic writing requires consistent use of the standard chosen and not a mixture of both. Differences in ASE and BSE are found in aspects such as pronunciation, spelling, and different meanings of the same word. The use of periods, commas and quotation marks was emphasised as being extremely important in academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 31-32).

The influence of ASE increased after the rise of the United States of America (USA) in global influence post-World War II due to its socio-economic, cultural, political and other types of power. In contrast, the international might of the British empire gradually waned with decolonisation (including the thirteen colonies that later became the USA in 1776 and over sixty countries that received their independence in the early to late twentieth century (Halloran 2014)). As a citizen of a country that the British once colonised, my writing is consciously influenced by BSE, though not consistently enforced and taught with sufficient details by the national educational system. However, the proliferation of computers, the influence of American culture and trade, and the proximity of the Caribbean to the USA have allowed shifts away from our colonial heritage. My writing unconsciously incorporates both ASE and BSE. I attribute this primarily to not being diligent enough to verify which English is used via dictionaries and style managers.

This *ACA-401D* module signals my need to move beyond the intermediate waters with which I have become accustomed and take a deep dive into a higher level of academic writing. The new waves generated by my journey in pursuing this degree will propel me to achieve the academic proficiency required for a doctoral degree.

5) PLAGIARISM

Chapter Four of the Coursepack examines the issue of plagiarism, which should be avoided at all costs. The term refers to situations where a ‘writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information’ such as using the words, ideas, data or visuals of a person by copying, pasting, quoting and even paragraphing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). The bedrock for this concern is driven by multiple considerations, including economic (acknowledging and compensating the originator while encouraging new data to be produced), which is protected by intellectual property legislation, and ethical (to engender high academic standards).

Proper citation is the key to avoiding plagiarism when writing my academic papers. As a recently matriculated student at Euclid University, I must adjust to and follow the required methods of in-text citation for publications such as books and works on the internet. The required format for books is to place in parenthesis the name of the author, followed by the number of the page from which the information was taken (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35). On the other hand, a list of works cited (also known as a bibliography or reference) must be placed at the end of the papers I prepare. This list is in a more formal format than the in-text citation. In the case of books, the author’s name appears first, followed by the date of publication, title of the book, place of publication and publisher (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 38). Some time has passed since I completed my master’s degree in law, so I hope any adjustments I need to make to change my habitual citation style will be swiftly implemented.

6) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

Chapter Five of the coursepack presents the style guide, or the approach to academic writing, required to be used by students at Euclid University when preparing papers. The Chicago Rules (Turabian) is recommended as the standard to be used by all students to enable uniformity and consistency in presenting the writing style for academic works. Style encompasses not only accurate deployment of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary. It extends to a host of other elements that together reflect the choices of the institution in reflecting literary excellence, which is not only standardised across institutions but portrays some level of uniqueness, as signalled by Euclid’s logo. My adherence to the Style Guide will impact a range of substantive and formatting aspects of my papers, such as using the prescribed templates to comply with the institutional branding and having a succinct length of sentences to promote readability and content structure (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41). In a more expansive context, this Chapter also allows

me to identify styles used by different entities and the usefulness of a style guide even for freelance writers who can customise a product to fit the needs of their clients.

The video that I watched (Cleenewerck 2016) was created to enable students to understand the whys and hows of the templates used in response to a student's concern about making corrections in Microsoft Word. The video reinforced the years of experience I have accumulated in document preparation using Microsoft Word and eliminating as many errors as possible before I submit a document. What added value to me was seeing a visual of the instructor correcting a paper, which helped me identify some errors in my writing and adjust my work accordingly.

7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I must endorse the purpose, effectiveness and frequent use of the Coursepack and supporting materials in aligning and elevating my essay writing skills in the academic setting of pursuing a higher degree at Euclid University. This guidance is essential for persons like me who are new to this institution and need to understand the academic writing culture of the institution. By the time I complete Period One (1), I should be more familiar with the standards for academic writing required by Euclid University. These should position me for faster completion of all mandated papers throughout my degree.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2016. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Halloran, Richard. 2014. 'The Sad, Dark End of the British Empire'. *POLITICO Magazine*. August 26, 2014. Accessed March 5, 2025. <https://www.politico.com/magazine/story/2014/08/the-sad-end-of-the-british-empire-110362>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.